

« THE EXPANSION OF CARBON FIBRES INTO INDUSTRY »

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It was just 10 years ago that carbon fibre reinforced plastics made its debut as an industrial application with the Bonas Loom Heald Frame⁽¹⁾. Given the variety of matrices, in which CF could work, plastics had already emerged as the one supporting material offering the most immediate promise. Since then the wide variety of applications in aerospace, sports goods and industry, involving all the primary CFRP characteristics have emphasised the versatility of CFRP⁽²⁾. Whilst the element of "gimmickry" or "one-up-manship" may assist in furthering the sphere of sports goods, and maximum performance at almost any price can be the order of the day in aerospace, the only permissible yardstick for industrial applications is COST-EFFECTIVENESS.

Progress in developing CFRC applications in this all-important sphere is reviewed and the potential CF demand is contemplated in the light of current developments.

INTRODUCTION

It was not by chance that textile machinery became the first target area for exploitation of carbon fibres within industry. Certainly the myriads of mass-conscious machine components, so apparent in this sphere, might well have attracted the eye of the development engineer in his search for potential applications. But, rather, it was the fact that textiles, which already constituted the main business of the leading U.K. manufacturer of C.F., naturally led to this area becoming the inevitable choice for first in-house experiments.

The Bonas Loom Heald Frame success was quickly followed by a number of other components also exploiting CFRP in textile machinery (3) (4) (5) (6). The intrusion of CFRP into this preserve of high performance metals, however, did not go unnoticed and expansion, from the bridge head formed by textile machinery and other medium volume applications, into the more important mass production industries, has been pursued as rapidly as technology would allow.

Experience during recent years has shown successful CFRP applications fall into 3 main categories.

1. Inertia-sensitive components, critical to the output of a machine, where CFRP achieves success by lifting the overall machine performance thus to justify a high cost of component (eg. Cost-effective applications employing long fibre components as pultrusion).
2. Critical or non-critical components which are costly to produce in traditional materials due to high labour content in their method of manufacture. CFRP achieves success, here, in providing equal or better performance at reduced cost. (eg. Cost-competitiveness using short fibre components via injection moulding).
3. Various cost-effective or cost-competitive end uses invoking the fibre properties of lubrication, negative thermal expansion, high electrical and thermal conductivity, X-ray transparency, etc.

Most of the primary characteristics of high specific strength and stiffness, with the resultant low inertia, have been applied to great advantage in the various high-speed reciprocating, oscillating or rotating masses pinpointed in textile machinery. The mounting demand for greater speed, to gain greater production, is being opposed by the need for reduced maintenance, reduced energy consumption and reduced noise. Between these conflicting interests traditional materials of construction have already been squeezed to the limit of their performance. The advent of CFRP has given a lift to these limitations to create a "virtuous circle" effect benefitting all other associated components of the machine right down to its foundations.

The strategy in pursuing applications to exploit CF in industry can be split into four stages.

1. Education in composites.
2. Identifying applications.
3. Producing the required types and forms of CF.
4. Developing suitable processes for conversion of CF into components.

The exercise of achieving full commercial success for a new material within the harsh realities of industry is not without its problems. The business of pinpointing and assessing the likely cost-effective CFRP components, as a primary task, is a sobering one. The follow-on process of developing the selected item through all the stages of experiment, prototype, pre-production and mass production, in such a new technology, is an exhausting one. There is the certainty of toil, tears and sweat, and perhaps a little blood, but the incentives are high and the rewards are great.

We must always remember, in developing applications, that technical performance must go hand in hand with costs, for, without both considerations, we cannot arrive at the vital cost-effective end product.

One of the rules which has evolved in exploring applications during the past decade can be stated:-

It is not until and unless traditional materials, traditional design and traditional methods of manufacture have been exploited to the full, and be still found wanting, that an economic case can usually be anticipated for CFRP. An exception to this rule arises when a change of method of manufacture, made possible by CFRP, can provide an easier, simpler and cheaper route to the end product. Such a route can be seen in the case of injection moulding whereby the completed article can be produced in a single operation. The first item, in a brief review of recently developed CFRP examples, confirms the results of adopting the injection moulding route can be dramatic, in giving both technical and economic benefits.

APPLICATIONS

1. SCROLL CAMBOX TRAVERSE GUIDE AND FOLLOWER (FIG.1).

The switch in materials of construction of this pair of inertia sensitive items from precision, ground-finished and hardened steel to CFRP mouldings with ceramic or steel inserts gave a reduction from 17.75 grms to 6.0 grms. mass.

Price comparisons made in 1975 showed the imported steel articles cost £6.00 per pair whereas the selling price for the home produced CFRP Mk I articles was £0.60 per pair. An improved design of the CFRP item resulted in the 1979 Mk II price rising to £1.17 per pair, but, meanwhile the steel imported articles price had risen to £15.40 per pair. Even allowing for a substantial factor to accommodate import duty, mark up etc., the CFRP items can thus be produced at a fraction of the equivalent components in traditional materials.

But the technical merits attributable to the material switch are also most significant and include, in addition to the substantially reduced inertia:

1. Elimination of need for cambox lubrication.
2. Reduction in internal box cleaning.
3. Increase in life of follower and guide.
4. Reduction in wear of guide rod.
5. Protection of scroll cam against damage.
6. Extension of life of bearing and shafts.
7. Reduction in machine downtime due to items 1-6.
8. Reduction in starting and running loads.
9. Reduction in noise level at standard speed.
10. Potential increase in machine speed due to reduced inertia.

While most of these factors listed are difficult to value, quantitatively, their combined benefit to overall machine performance is left in no doubt.

2. THE CFRP PICKSTICK FOR SHUTTLE LOOMS (FIG.2).

The pultruded CFRP pickstick is the modern replacement for the natural/laminated wood pickstick used in traditional looms to catapult the shuttle across the machine. It is interesting to note that, here, one of mans oldest materials of construction is being replaced by one of the most recent materials. Indeed, CFRP has been described, quite aptly, as a super quality wood but with 15 times the stiffness and 10 times the strength. Certainly, manufacturers of picksticks in wood have exploited the material to its limit, with careful selection of timber,

densification, lamination, shaping etc., but this still fails to meet the very arduous duty demanded of picksticks in fast, wide looms.

Cost of CFRP pultruded picksticks, at £40 per pair and some 10 times that of the wooden stick, appears to be rather formidable. This cost however, represents <1% of the total installed loom cost and, once again, we need only to examine the list of benefits in machine performance to see, clearly, the cost-effectiveness of this highly stressed component.

ADVANTAGES OVER WOOD

1. 60% in mass only.
2. Fully elastic within limited strain.
3. Virtually fatigue failure free.
4. Operational life increased by factor of 10.

IMPROVEMENT IN LOOM PERFORMANCE

1. Increased permissible loom speed (optimum for product quality etc).
200 cm wide loom - 210 ppm to 235 ppm.
315 cm wide loom - 160 ppm to 175 ppm.

3. THE CFRP REINFORCED BARS TO WARP KINITTING MACHINE (FIG.3.4).

This development exploits the negative thermal expansion property of C.F. Inertia considerations have required the use of traditional lightweight alloys of magnesium and aluminum for the long bars reciprocating at speeds of up to 2000 cycles/minute in the action of knitting. Unfortunately, these alloys involve a high rate of thermal expansion coupled with a low modulus which inhibits high speed and precise knitting. Both these complications can be eliminated by the use of pultruded CFRP inserts bonded into recesses formed in the metal. The small, but negative, thermal expansion of the CFRP with its high modulus contains the large, and positive, expansion of the low modulus alloy to a level approaching that of steel thus rendering changes in shop temperature no longer critical. Increase in stiffness and reduction in weight can permit additional machine speed and improve product quality.

Again, we can see the extra cost of the CFRP fitted items rapidly offset by the increased performance of the complete machine. A factory floor study made in 1974 gave an increase in cost for the CFRP fitted bar of £384 per machine. Additional profits, derived from the resultant 12% increase in production, plus improved product quality generated by the modification, gave £416 per machine to show a return on capital in 11 months.

The widening use of fibre reinforced plastics including CFRP, for chemical plant applications⁽⁷⁾, emphasises their special immunity to pitting, crevice corrosion and other localised degradation, compared with the higher quality metals, as extras to the normal advantages of reinforced plastics. Additionally, the combination of special characteristics of high specific heat coupled with high specific modulus⁽⁸⁾ puts a unique value on CFRP not only for aerospace but also in industrial applications. Again, we are seeing additions to this family of materials which offer a wide variety of characteristics many of which have yet to be exploited in full. Recent movements in the chemical plant sphere⁽⁹⁾ involving the use of long fibres may well stimulate a spin-off in other areas. Here, the characteristics of the resin system is all important for the performance of the composite is as good as the resin and no better. An expanding choice of resin systems now available, however, provide a list of attributes very encouraging to the designer and fabricator, including:

1. Excellent chemical resistance to most media (solvents, acids, bases and their various combinations).
2. Resistance to chemical attack at elevated temperatures.
3. Excellent retention of physical properties at elevated temperatures.
4. Flexibility with safety (significant latitude for process changes, accidental spills, thermal upsets and modifications).
5. Easy fabrication by hand lay-up, spray-up, filament winding, moulding or pultrusion.
6. Improved toughness permitting fabrication and transportation of large structures.

Three such items, recently completed but still under development, can once again measure up to the criteria of cost-effectiveness.

4. CFRP SPARGE PIPE FOR ACID WASH MACHINE (FIG.5)

Requirements for the component involve spanning the wash machine, ca 2 metres wide, to distribute evenly across the machine a liquor of weak sulphuric acid at ca 90°C containing dissolved H₂S and CS₂. Removal of the sparge pipe for cleaning, etc, puts a substantial premium on lightness to avoid the hazard of machine hood encroachment to the Operative when lifting out the pipe. Various proprietary plastic, ceramic and metal compositions failed to meet this primary requirement without suffering chemical attack or undue deflection or distortion of tube. The CFRP pipe produced, which had a wall thickness of 1.5mm and bore of 75mm, fully satisfied the mechanical and chemical resistance requirements.

Weight of the CFRP tube, at 1.2 Kg, represented approximately half that of the lightest alternative material.

Cost of the tube, at £70 each, the construction of which comprised a combination of woven and non-woven CF fabric surfaced by CF tissue, approximated the cheapest alternative material tried even on a small quantity basis. Given a modest scale of production some reduction in this price is anticipated.

5. C.F.R.P. Tubing for Heat Exchangers (Fig.6).

Details available for this application, which is still under development, are strictly limited but, here, the primary objective is to produce a CFRP thin-wall tube competitive both in straight cost and cost-effectiveness with the traditional tube in graphite. Despite a reduced thermal conductivity value compared with graphite, the thin-wall construction of the CFRP tube generally compensates for this and the vastly superior mechanical properties of CFRP eliminates the susceptibility to fracture hazard of the graphite. Other technical merits expected of the CFRP item include:

1. Reduced size and weight of heat exchanger (reduced pitch of tube in tube plates).
2. Better resistance to thermal shock.
3. Reduced susceptibility to growth of scale/deposits.
4. Easier removal of deposits.
5. Increased permissible working pressures.
6. Elimination of risk of catastrophic failures.

The sum total of advantages listed above indicate the substantial technical superiority of the CFRP tube. It is interesting to note, also, earlier work⁽¹⁰⁾ has shown that plastic tubes for heat exchangers provide a better performance than established theory predicts.

Although costings have yet to be confirmed the initial assessment indicates CFRP should be competitive with the graphite tube, on a straight cost basis and that cost of production for large volume could be substantially less.

6. CFRP SPARK PROOF WRENCH/SPANNER (FIG.7.8)

The ever increasing cost of beryllium copper, a standard material for non-sparking tools, has led to development of a CFRP alternative for, firstly, an open ended spanner and, subsequently, a large wrench. A comparison of the mechanical properties of these two materials is shown in Appendix 1. Although the mechanical performance of CFRP, in terms of U.T.S. and Modulus, is not unfavourable, there are three main design considerations which indicate the need for a marriage of materials.

1. CFRP material softness (giving indentation at high point loadings - ie corners of the nut).
2. Poor I.L.S. value between layers of fibre around the jaw.
3. Transfer of high torque between jaws and handle.

Utilisation of a B.C. metal liner in the jaw, together with internal steel webs coupling jaw to handle, provide an adequate cover for these considerations.

Fabrication of these single, experimental components, with their strictly orientated fibre and complex construction, obviously incurs high labour costs. Manufacture of such items, in quantity, will force the development of special purpose fibre laying machines and moulding techniques. It will probably be necessary for a demand of some 50,000 units per annum to justify the development of such a machine, where its own cost can be reimbursed over a period of, say, 2 years without imposing an unduly high overhead on to the cost of the individual component. An indicative assessment showed that the CFRP metal fitted component could compete with the traditional material item on straight cost given this quantity of production.

Whilst such a fabrication as the spark proof spanner or wrench for chemical plants may not, in itself, incur the demand necessary to justify special purpose machinery, it is believed the spin-off in the much wider area of structural applications could well produce such a demand. Typical components which come to mind include levers, cranks, connecting rods and linkages where mass and inertia are critical. It is hoped, therefore, this development in the chemical plant sphere may stimulate similar thinking in the more important structural area.

THE FUTURE

Any involvement in the development of a new technology, such as carbon fibres, cannot for long avoid speculation on its expansion and the offerings of opinion and forecasts are now increasing markedly. There are many considerations to be made.

The advent of SMC and DMC, in conjunction with low profile resins, has seen an inroad into areas where metals are now being superseded⁽¹¹⁾.

The need to extend the provision of various forms of CF and new process equipment for converting these into end products has certainly been emphasised⁽¹²⁾.

Plastics, generally, are now occupying bigger and bigger roles in automobiles with CFRP leading the field as a potential cost-effective material in the high performance areas. Recently reported developments⁽¹³⁾ in the automotive world confirm some 160 experimental components have already been produced including dynamic items such as drive shafts, leaf springs, door hinges, valve push rods and also vehicle frame, body and chassis.

There is a need, now, to cultivate confidence in the use of CF in all the mass production spheres. Whilst the first CFRP component in production, an air conditioner mounting bracket⁽¹⁴⁾, represents a very modest venture, it does provide experience at minimum risk, upon which the forthcoming high duty applications can build.

Continuing growth in demand for carbon fibre is assured. However, earlier indications⁽¹⁵⁾⁽¹⁶⁾ in the disposition of demand for C.F. between the three most important spheres of Aerospace, Sports Goods and Industrial applications is likely to change dramatically in the late 80's in favour of the industrial area. Whilst applications in aerospace could see an order of magnitude increase in CF demand in, say, 10 years the impact of CFRP upon industry, in general, and the automotive and domestic appliance spheres, in particular, suggests an increase by a factor of 50 highly probable. An attempt at forecasting CF demands, given this expansion of CF in the automotive and other spheres, is shown in Appendix 2, bearing in mind C.F. can reinforce matrices other than plastics.

Certainly, the question of suitability of carbon fibre reinforced composites, in their competition with metal and other traditional materials, has become resolved into an issue which is no longer one of "if" but rather one of "when".

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REFERENCES

- 1 TOVEY H.T., 'Fibre Technology at Bonas Bros' - P.E.R.A. Conf.-Fibre Technology in Eng. April 1970.
- 2 LUCAS R, 'Carbon Fibres - The Versatile Performer'. C.M.E. Journal April 1973.
- 3 LUCAS R, 'Exploitation of CF Composites in Special Purpose Plant' P.E.R.A. Conf - Applications of Fibre Composites, September 1971.
- 4 LUCAS R, 'Applications of C.F. to High Speed Loom Sleys' 'Composites' March 1975.
- 5 LUCAS R, 'CFRP Exploitation in Textile Machinery' - PRI Conf. Research Projects in Reinforced Plastics, London February 1976.
- 6 TREWIN E.M., et al.'C.F. Advances the Scope of Thermoplastics in Engineering Applications' PRI Conf. Reinf. Plastics II, November 1977.
- 7 GEGNER PAUL J., 'Using Reinforced Plastics' Chemtech, November 1979
- 8 DIEFENDORF R.J, et al. 'Carbon Fibres' Fibre Producer, December 1979.
- 9 LUCAS R. 'Use of CFRP in Corrosive Environments' Paper 11. Symposium on R.P. N.E.L. September 1979.
- 10 NARRAWAY R, 'Giving Heat Exchangers a Better Life Factor'. Processing, June 1978.
- 11 MOHR J.S., et al. Preform & SMC Methods for matched Die Molding. S.P.I. Handbook of Technology & Eng. February 1973.
- 12 PHILLIPS L.N., 'Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastics - The First Fifteen Years'. P & R Int. November 1978.

- 13/14 McCANN MICHAEL K, Article & Special Supplement - Automotive Industries
September 1979.
- 15 LUCAS R, 'Application of CFC in General Engineering' Paper 40 P.R.I.
Int. Conf. on C.F. February 1974.
- 16 TREWIN EDWARD M, 'The Engineering Applications for C.F. in Thermosetting
and Thermoplastics Materials' Paper 2.
Intern.Eng. Conf. N.E.C. Birmingham, October 1979.

APPENDIX I - COMPARISON OF CFRP WITH BERYLLIUM COPPER

PROPERTIES OF BERYLLIUM COPPER

	<u>U.T.S.</u> (G.Pa)	<u>70% Yield</u> (G.Pa.)	<u>Modulus</u> (G.Pa.)
a). Softened condition	0.48	0.34	-
b). Heat treated	1.21	0.85	-
c). H.t ^d . and cold worked	1.35	0.95	135

PROPERTIES OF 60% vv CF UNIDIRECTIONAL IN EPOXY

	<u>U.T.S. (Non-Yield)</u> (G.Pa.)	<u>Modulus</u> (G.Pa.)
A - S	1.45	110
XA - S	1.90	125
H.M.	1.5	190

APPENDIX 2 WESTERN WORLD MARKETS FOR CAROBON FIBRES. (TONNES PER ANNUM)

			1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1990
AEROSPACE			225	325	450	600	750	900	1100	3500
SPORTS GOODS			225	300	450	600	800	1000	1250	4000
I D U S T R Y	AU -	I.C.ENGINES (Exc1 ^g C.I.)	1	2	5	10	20	50	75	2500
	TO -	C.I.ENGINES	2	5	8	20	50	75	115	5000
	MO -	TRANSMISSION	7	12	20	30	75	125	175	3500
	TI -	SUSPENSION	8	15	25	75	150	225	350	10000
	VE -	CHASSIS/FRAME	5	10	15	30	50	75	100	2000
DOMESTIC APPLIANCES			6	10	15	30	60	100	200	2500
I N D U S T R Y	TEXTILE MACHINERY		14	20	30	50	75	95	125	250
	CHEMICAL PLANT		17	12	20	30	50	70	125	1000
	PROCESS PLANT		5	8	20	30	50	75	125	1000
	MINING		9	15	25	40	75	125	200	750
CIVIL ENGINEERING			4	8	15	30	50	75	150	2000
ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING			5	8	15	30	50	75	125	1000
RAIL TRANSPORT			6	10	20	30	50	75	125	750
MARINE			5	8	15	30	60	80	150	1000
MEDICAL			2	5	10	15	20	30	40	250
MILITARY			7	12	20	30	80	135	250	4000
MUSICAL INSTRUMENTS			1	2	4	10	25	40	80	3000
SUNDRY UNDEFINED			6	13	18	30	50	75	140	2000
TOTALS			550	800	1200	1750	2500	3500	5000	50000

Fig 1 : Scroll Cambox Traverse Guide and Follower.
L to R : Steel, MK I CFRP, MK II CFRP.

(Courtesy : Courtaulds Engineering Ltd)

Fig 2 : CFRP Pickstick for Shuttle Loom

(Courtesy : Carbon Fibers Division, Courtaulds Ltd)

Fig 3 : CFRP Reinforcing Bars to Warp Knitting Machine.
(Courtesy : Research Division, Courtaulds Ltd)

Fig 4: CFRP Reinforcing Bars to Warp Knitting Machine.

(Courtesy : Research Division, Courtaulds Ltd)

Fig 5 : GFRP Sparge Pipe for Acid Wash Machine.
(Courtesy : Courtaulds Engineering Ltd)

Fig 6 : CFRP Tubing for Heat Exchangers with Graphite Tube Above.

(Courtesy : Research Division, Courtaulds Ltd and R.C.E. Ltd)

Fig 7 : CFRP Spark Proof Spanner with Beryllium Copper Item Below.

(Courtesy : Research Division, Courtaulds Ltd)

Fig 8 : CFRP Spark-Proof Wrench with B.C. Item Above.

(Courtesy : Research Division, Courtaulds Ltd)